

Laserlab-Europe Technology Roadmap 2026

Content

Executive Summary..... 3

Technology Roadmap 4

 Introduction..... 4

 I - Health and Medicine..... 4

 II – Clean energy 7

 1 - Photovoltaics, batteries and clean fuels..... 7

 2 - Laser fusion..... 9

 III – Industry and manufacturing 12

 IV – Space 14

 V – Security..... 16

 VI – Communications and computing 17

 VII – Environment, Climate and Agrifood..... 19

 VIII – Cultural Heritage 21

 IX – Science at the extremes 23

 Outlook 26

Glossary 28

Composition of the Scientific Writing Group..... 29

LASERLAB-EUROPE AISBL 30

Executive Summary

Laser science and technology are key enablers of Europe's strategic autonomy, innovation capacity and industrial competitiveness, with transformative impact across a broad range of societal domains, including health, energy, security and climate. Maintaining and strengthening Europe's leadership in this field requires coordinated action to address a set of critical, cross-cutting scientific and technological challenges.

This roadmap builds on the comprehensive landscape analysis conducted by Laserlab-Europe and published in 2023, which mapped Europe's capabilities and highlighted emerging trends, strategic opportunities and critical needs across the laser ecosystem. Moving beyond this analysis, the present document identifies priorities for the coming decade, focusing on the key developments required to translate scientific excellence into societal, technological and economic impact.

Achieving the objectives of this roadmap will require coordinated investment in human capital, long-term research and innovation funding and the sustained operational readiness of European research and technology infrastructures at the highest level. Strengthening Europe's talent pipeline, supporting the full innovation chain from fundamental research to industrial deployment, and ensuring access to state-of-the-art laser facilities are essential to maintain leadership and convert scientific excellence into strategic capability and societal benefit.

The impact of these investments can be further amplified by leveraging the complementarity of laser infrastructures with other major European photon and particle research facilities (e.g., X-ray free-electron lasers). Such coordination will enable scientific and technological advances that no single platform could achieve alone and reinforce Europe's position at the forefront of next-generation photonics and laser technologies.

Technology Roadmap

Introduction

Laser science and technology underpin a wide range of strategic capabilities across Europe, from fundamental science and advanced manufacturing to healthcare, clean energy, security and environmental monitoring. Over recent decades, Europe has established a globally leading position in many areas of laser research, photonics and research infrastructures. However, the accelerating pace of technological competition, the increasing complexity of innovation ecosystems and the urgency of major societal challenges now require a more coordinated and forward-looking approach to investment, development and deployment.

In this context, Laserlab-Europe initiated a structured roadmap exercise to identify the key scientific and technological priorities that will shape the evolution of laser-based technologies over the coming decade. This effort builds directly on the comprehensive landscape analysis published in 2023, which provided a detailed overview of existing European capabilities, infrastructures and emerging trends, while identifying both strengths and critical gaps within the current ecosystem. While the landscape analysis offered a valuable snapshot of the state of the art, it also highlighted the need to move beyond description toward prioritization, coordination and strategic alignment.

Many of the most critical challenges in laser science are inherently cross-cutting, spanning multiple application domains while relying on common technological building blocks, including advanced laser sources, optical materials, diagnostics and precision laser beam control. The present roadmap therefore identifies, first, a set of core scientific questions and technological challenges and, second, articulate their implications across major societal, industrial and scientific application domains: health and medicine, clean energy, including laser fusion, industry and manufacturing, security and space, communications and computing, environment and climate, cultural heritage and science at the extremes.

This structure reflects a deliberate effort to bridge the gap between technology push and societal demand. By organizing the roadmap around application domains while preserving the coherence of the underlying technological challenges, the document makes explicit how advances in laser science can translate into concrete societal and economic impacts. It also facilitates alignment with European policy frameworks, which are increasingly organized around mission-oriented and impact-driven priorities.

Ultimately, this roadmap aims to provide a clear, coherent and actionable framework to guide future investments, strengthen coordination at the European level, and ensure that Europe remains at the forefront of laser science and its transformative applications.

I - Health and Medicine

Health and medicine increasingly rely on laser-based technologies that enhance disease understanding, diagnostics, therapy and personalized medicine. Lasers now support imaging, spectroscopy, surgical procedures, regenerative medicine, particle-based radiotherapy and high-sensitivity chemical analysis. Their impact stems from precise control over wavelength, pulse duration, repetition rate and beam geometry, enabling interactions with biological matter across photochemical, photothermal, photomechanical, nonlinear and plasma-mediated regimes.

Future clinical systems must combine advanced performance with compactness, robustness, cost efficiency and regulatory readiness. Integration of diagnostic and therapeutic

capabilities, with real-time optical feedback, will be a defining feature of next-generation medical photonics.

Lasers enable unique capabilities essential to modern healthcare:

- non-invasive, label-free access to structural and molecular information in living tissues,
- ultrafast temporal resolution from femtoseconds to nanoseconds for probing biological dynamics,
- spectral selectivity for targeted photochemistry, drug activation and optogenetics,
- high spatial precision for surgical cutting, ablation and photo-disruption,
- fibre-based delivery for minimally invasive diagnostics and interventions,
- secondary-particle and X-ray generation for advanced radiotherapy and imaging,
- compatibility with AI and computational modelling for automated and quantitative interpretation.

These strengths underpin a broad spectrum of laser-enabled clinical and research applications.

Challenge I.1 - Integrated multimodal laser-based imaging and spectroscopy

Future optical systems must provide quantitative, real-time and label-free information on tissue structure, function and molecular composition. Techniques such as optical coherence tomography, photo-acoustics, fluorescence lifetime imaging, spontaneous/coherent Raman spectroscopy, nonlinear optical microscopy all impose stringent requirements on spectral flexibility, ultrafast pulse control, stability and compactness. Advances in robust, tuneable ultrafast sources, especially fibre-based architectures, along with improved scanning, synchronization and high-throughput data pipelines, are essential to translate multimodal imaging into clinical practice.

Milestones

- By 2030, integrated multimodal imaging and spectroscopy platforms should reach TRL 4-5, enabling real-time label-free molecular tissue characterization in clinically relevant environments.
- By 2035, standardized and interoperable multimodal optical platforms providing real-time quantitative feedback should become routinely available at TRL 7-8, supporting deployment in clinical workflows.

Challenge I.2 - Laser-assisted interventions with real-time optical guidance

The convergence of laser-based imaging/spectroscopy and therapeutic energy delivery opens opportunities for precision surgery, minimally invasive interventions and closed-loop treatment. Photochemical, photothermal and photomechanical processes must be delivered with high spatial accuracy and robust monitoring. Surgical precision depends on precise beam steering, stable fibre delivery, pulse-to-pulse energy control and real-time feedback loops. Integration of diagnostic–therapeutic platforms (theranostics, image-guided surgery, optically steered ablation) will require robust calibration, safety standards and user-friendly interfaces.

Milestones

- By 2030, compact fibre-delivered laser systems integrating optical guidance should demonstrate TRL 4-5 capabilities for adaptive minimally invasive interventions.
- By 2035, certified closed-loop diagnostic-therapeutic laser platforms should mature to TRL 7-8 to support personalized image-guided treatment workflows.

Challenge I.3 - High-power lasers for particle- and radiation-based therapies

Laser-driven secondary sources of particles and radiation can enable flexible, compact and potentially cost-effective, radiotherapy and imaging systems. A key strength of this approach is its versatility: a single high-power laser platform can generate a range of ultra-short (from femtoseconds to nanoseconds) particle and radiation pulses, adaptable to different clinical needs.

Ion acceleration is of critical importance in oncology: the Bragg peak enables selective energy deposition in the treatment zone, reducing side effects. Using current technology, 100 TW – 1 PW primary lasers generate protons in the 50 -160 MeV range. However, achieving the required irradiance of 10^{20} - 10^{21} W/cm² on target will demand PW and even 10 PW laser sources, significant advances being thus needed to reduce size, complexity and operating costs. When directed onto specific targets, these laser-accelerated proton pulses can also induce nuclear reactions and generate medically relevant isotopes, to be used in theranostics. Compared to conventional cyclotrons, laser-driven systems could be more compact and flexible, an advantage particularly valuable for short-lived isotopes used in PET imaging and targeted radiotherapy.

Laser wakefield acceleration of electrons by 100 TW – 1 PW, Ti:sapphire or post-compressed Yb, laser systems, may unlock the full potential of FLASH radiotherapy if shot-to-shot reproducibility and stability are ensured. High-brightness and monochromatic K α X-ray sources can be generated using few-TW ultrafast lasers focused on ribbons of pure metals such as molybdenum or copper. Compared to conventional broadband X-ray tubes, they are particularly valuable in phase-contrast imaging and spectral computed tomography, offering improved image contrast and reduced patient dose.

Milestones

- By 2030, stable 100 TW - 1 PW laser platforms should enable reproducible proton/electron acceleration and preclinical (TRL 3-4) FLASH radiotherapy studies, while laser-driven K α X-ray sources should support advanced imaging R&D.
- By 2035, prototype compact laser-driven particle and K α X-ray systems should progress toward TRL 5-6, paving the way for hospital-compatible radiotherapy and high-contrast imaging prototype platforms.

Challenge I.4: Lasers for regenerative and personalized medicine

Laser-assisted bioprinting, photo-biomodulation and tissue-engineering workflows require precise, gentle energy delivery compatible with living cells and complex bio-inks. In vitro cell deposition often relies on nanosecond near-IR - IR sources; in vivo deposition demands mid-IR fibre delivery leveraging water absorption. Stability, compactness, energy control, cost and absence of contaminants are central requirements. These technologies support organoid engineering, vascularized constructs and personalized tissue repair.

Milestones

- By 2030, high-viability laser bioprinting and compact mid-IR fibre-delivered systems should demonstrate TRL 4-5 capabilities for validated in vitro and early in vivo tissue deposition.
- By 2035, integrated laser bio-fabrication platforms supporting personalized regenerative medicine workflows (combining bioprinting, imaging and optical stimulation) should mature toward TRL 6-7.

Challenge I.5: Cost-effective, tuneable lasers for photomedicine, ophthalmology, diagnostics and aesthetics

Photodynamic therapy, photoacoustic imaging, photo-pharmacology, optogenetics, multiphoton microscopy and ophthalmic surgery depend on tailored wavelength control, short pulses, beam-pointing stability and affordability. Applications in aesthetics, dermatology and refractive surgery require robust, clinically safe, low-cost lasers with precise dosimetry and smart tracking. High-rep-rate ytterbium and fibre-based post-compressed systems will play an increasing role, providing tunability and compactness needed for broad clinical adoption.

Laser-based chiral spectroscopy is emerging as a powerful tool in pharmacology, where enantiomeric purity is essential ($\approx 95\%$ of drugs are chiral). Circularly polarized ultrafast light combined with photoelectron detection can analyse chiral mixtures within seconds, outperforming chromatography. To reach industrial adoption, long-term-stable ultrafast fibre

lasers (tens of watts, <100 fs, >1 MHz repetition rate) with compact, cost-efficient packaging are needed.

Milestones

- By 2030, compact tuneable ultrafast lasers for photodynamic therapy, photo-acoustics, multiphoton imaging, refractive surgery and preclinical chiral diagnostics should become validated at TRL 5-6.
- By 2035, affordable alignment-free ultrafast laser platforms at TRL 7-8 should enable broad deployment of precision photomedicine and enantiospecific pharmaceutical analysis.

Challenge I.6: Data integration, digital twins and regulatory-ready clinical systems

Modern optical imaging and spectroscopy produce increasingly rich, multimodal datasets. Extracting clinically meaningful information requires combining optical measurements with physics-based models and AI-supported methods. Compliance with the EU Medical Device Regulation also demands validated algorithms, standardized workflows and transparent calibration procedures. Longer-term, patient-specific digital representations integrating optical data, mechanistic models and longitudinal information will support personalized diagnostics and therapy planning.

Milestones

- By 2030, validated optical-AI analysis frameworks and MDR-aligned workflows are expected, at TRL 5-6, to support clinical decision-making and interoperable data handling.
- By 2035, patient-specific digital-twin platforms integrating multimodal optical data should progress toward TRL 6-7 for personalized diagnostics and therapy planning.

Summary

Laser-enabled healthcare stands at the threshold of a new technological era. Advances in ultrafast laser sources, high-repetition-rate systems, multimodal imaging, optical guidance, laser-driven particle sources, and photonic integration will transform diagnostics and therapy. Compact, stable, alignment-free lasers with spectral flexibility will bring nonlinear microscopy, OCT, photo-acoustics and photodynamic therapy into routine clinical environments. Laser-driven accelerators and Ka sources will expand therapeutic and imaging capabilities while reducing system footprint. Concurrent advances in computational modelling, AI, and MDR-aligned validation frameworks will ensure that optical systems are robust, interpretable and certifiable. By 2035, the convergence of imaging, spectroscopy and intervention will enable real-time, quantitative, minimally invasive medical care, improving precision, safety and patient outcomes across the entire healthcare continuum.

II – Clean energy

1 - Photovoltaics, batteries and clean fuels

Achieving a climate-neutral energy system requires rapid progress in the generation, storage and conversion of clean energy. Solar power, advanced batteries and sustainable fuels, such as green hydrogen, will form the core of this transition. To unlock their full potential, Europe must develop materials and devices with higher efficiency, longer lifetimes and scalable, low-cost manufacturing routes.

Laser technologies play a dual strategic role in this effort. Ultrafast laser spectroscopy provides access to the fundamental photophysical and catalytic processes that limit device performance, while laser-based micro/nano-processing enables the controlled fabrication of

advanced materials and components. Together, they constitute a powerful engine for accelerating materials discovery, device optimization and industrial scale-up.

Solar and clean-fuel conversion rely on interlinked processes (light absorption, charge generation, transport and catalytic turnover) spanning femtoseconds to microseconds and nanometres to micrometres. Many of the bottlenecks (recombination, limited charge mobility, catalyst degradation) can only be understood through time-resolved, operando probes and addressed through precision nano-structuring. State-of-the-art laser platforms already enable:

- femtosecond-attosecond spectroscopy to resolve electron localization, hot-carrier cooling and ultrafast charge separation,
- mid-IR, THz, sum frequency generation and 2D electronic spectroscopy to track catalytic intermediates, photoconductivity and interfacial dynamics,
- laser ablation, crystallization, laser-induced periodic surface structuration, pulse laser deposition, multiphoton lithography and laser-induced forward transfer for surface engineering, catalyst design and fabrication of custom 3D micro/nanostructures.

However, these tools remain limited in stability, tunability, repetition rate and accessibility. Unlocking their full impact requires targeted technological advances.

Challenge II.1: Ultrafast laser platforms for high-resolution spectroscopy

Robust ultrafast sources offering repetition rates in the MHz range, sub-20 fs pulse duration and broad tunability, from the UV to the mid-IR, are key technological requirements for probing coherent charge transfer and catalytic initiation steps. Achieving these performances alongside shot-to-shot stability better than 0.1 % would significantly improve measurement sensitivity. For widespread use in photovoltaics, electrocatalysis and battery diagnostics, these capabilities must ultimately be delivered in compact table-top systems compatible with operando environments. Advanced fibre-based ultrafast laser architectures may, in that context, offer a particularly promising pathway to bridge the gap between laboratory-scale systems and ready-to-use platforms, enabling, e.g., adaptation to various experimental and industrial requirements while reducing system complexity and cost.

Milestones

- By 2030, compact and tuneable (from IR to UV) few-cycle lasers that operate stably at repetition rates higher than 1 MHz should be available at TRL 4-5 for operando ultrafast spectroscopy of solar and catalytic devices in order to resolve femtosecond-to-microsecond pathways of charge and mass transport.
- By 2035, industrial-compatible ultrafast sources for inline spectroscopy and advanced manufacturing, reaching TRL 6-7 should start to be deployed.

Challenge II.2: Laser-assisted micro/nano-structuring for high-efficiency devices

Advanced laser-assisted micro- and nano-structuring techniques are required to engineer materials with controlled morphology, high active-surface area and optimized charge- and mass-transport pathways. Approaches such as LIPSS, PLD, laser crystallization and multiphoton processing, offer unique capabilities for tailoring catalytic interfaces, semiconductor layers and electrode architectures, with much higher precision than conventional methods. For clean-energy applications, such as the fabrication of photovoltaic components, fuel-cell interfaces and battery materials. these techniques must still evolve toward reproducibility, scalability and stability.

Milestones

- By 2030, reproducible laser nano-structuring should achieve TRL 4-5 for pilot-scale fabrication of 3D photovoltaic and catalytic components.
- By 2035, high-throughput laser fabrication of multifunctional electrodes and catalysts should be achieved.

Challenge II.3: Integration and industrialization

Integrating laser-based diagnostics and fabrication methods into realistic manufacturing environments requires major progress in process stability, throughput and compatibility with large-area and roll-to-roll platforms. Ensuring that ultrafast spectroscopies and precision structuring methods can operate reliably under industrial conditions would allow real-time quality control, accelerated materials screening and streamlined device prototyping. The development of such integrated workflows would support the transition from laboratory demonstrations to pilot-line validation and, eventually, to industrial-scale production of clean-energy systems.

Milestones

- By 2030, PLD/LIFT-fabricated thin films should be integrated into prototype devices and integrated laser-processing and diagnostic platforms validated at TRL 5-6 in pilot manufacturing environments.
- By 2035, these platforms should reach TRL 7-8 to support large-scale clean-energy manufacturing, including roll-to-roll-compatible fabrication and qualification.

Summary

Laser technologies are becoming a central driver of innovation in clean-energy materials and devices. Their unique ability to resolve ultrafast charge-transfer and catalytic processes, together with their precision in shaping materials at the micro- and nanoscale, is opening new pathways to higher-efficiency photovoltaics, advanced batteries, and sustainable fuel production. As laser platforms gain stability, tunability and compactness, they will increasingly enable operando diagnostics and reproducible fabrication methods that conventional techniques cannot provide.

Over the next decade, progress in ultrafast laser sources and laser-based structuring is expected to accelerate the full innovation cycle, from fundamental understanding of energy-conversion mechanisms to the development of prototype devices and the validation of scalable manufacturing routes. The integration of these tools into pilot-line environments will support the emergence of laser-engineered components for photovoltaics, fuel cells and hydrogen-based energy systems. Such advances will contribute to more durable materials, improved conversion efficiencies and cleaner, more resilient energy infrastructures.

By 2035, the combined impact of laser spectroscopy, laser processing and data-driven materials design is anticipated to play a significant role in enabling commercially viable clean-energy technologies. This will support Europe's broader decarbonization efforts, including the deployment of hydrogen-based mobility and maritime applications and strengthen the overall transition toward a climate-neutral, sustainable energy system.

2 - Laser fusion

Harnessing the energy released by the fusion of light nuclei has long been viewed as a promising route to clean, carbon-free power with minimal long-lived radioactive waste. Laser-driven inertial fusion for energy has gained renewed global momentum following recent ignition experiments at the U.S. National Ignition Facility that demonstrated net energy yield, with scientific energy gains greater than 4. These breakthroughs confirm the feasibility of laser-driven fusion but also highlight the significant technological gaps between single-shot experimental facilities and high-repetition, high-efficiency systems required for energy production. Future IFE power plants will require robust target designs, MJ-class pulses delivered at multi-Hz repetition rates with high wall-plug efficiency, together with high-throughput additive manufacturing of advanced micro-structured targets, tightly-controlled target injection and tracking, and radiation-tolerant optics and diagnostics. Progress toward these

goals demands coordinated advances in laser architectures, materials, plasma physics, automation, and systems engineering.

Laser technologies provide the fundamental capabilities required to advance inertial fusion energy toward an energy-relevant regime:

- precise, high-power energy delivery enabling the rapid compression and heating of DT fuel capsules on nanosecond timescales,
- exceptional accurate temporal and spatial pulse shaping, required to master implosion symmetry, suppress hydrodynamic instabilities and optimize coupling efficiency,
- high-resolution laser-based diagnostics, including X-ray backlighting, Thomson scattering, imaging spectroscopy and optical probing of capsule implosion dynamics,
- laser-plasma interaction platforms for studying energy coupling, instability growth and other relevant underlying physics mechanisms under reactor-relevant conditions.

Taken together, these laser capabilities provide the essential physical and technological basis for progressing from single-shot ignition demonstrations to reliable, repetitive operation compatible with future fusion-energy systems.

Challenge II.4 - High-energy, high-repetition-rate lasers with good wall-plug efficiency

Energy-relevant inertial fusion requires laser drivers far beyond the present state of the art. Most designs for a 1 GW-class IFE plant assume fusion gains of ≈ 100 , implying that the driver must deliver 10 MW of average optical power, corresponding to 1–3 MJ pulses at 10 Hz. To make this viable, laser wall-plug efficiencies must exceed 10%, so that only 50–100 MW of electrical power is recycled internally. Current ignition-scale systems, such as NIF, deliver UV pulses, with an efficiency of less than 1%, every 8 hours (to allow heat dissipation in the lasing material). The gap to IFE requirements therefore spans five orders of magnitude in repetition rate and a factor ≈ 20 in efficiency. The most advanced high-average-power lasers to date, such as the diode-pumped Yb:YAG DiPOLE system (1 kW/10 Hz average power, 20% efficiency), illustrate both progress and challenge scale: extrapolating such architectures to MJ energies.

Milestones

- By 2030, fusion-driver architectures should establish TRL 3-4 capabilities for sub-kJ operation at improved repetition rate (up to a few Hz, solving issues related to thermal management and to damage thresholds of optical components) and wall-plug efficiency (approaching the percent level).
- By 2035, damage management concepts should reach maturity enabling multi-kJ multi-Hz laser systems – with wall-plug efficiencies exceeding 5% - to progress toward TRL 5-6 and validate MJ-class architectures.

Challenge II.5 - Impact of spectral bandwidth on laser-plasma interaction

At IFE-relevant intensities, laser-plasma instabilities, such as stimulated Raman and Brillouin scattering, are resonantly driven by plasma waves, which grow exponentially beyond certain thresholds, reflecting incident laser light and generating fast electrons that preheat the fuel. Both effects substantially degrade implosion symmetry and increase the laser energy required for ignition, potentially by an order of magnitude. Numerical studies indicate that a broad spectral bandwidth (i.e., a spread of the laser light spectrum in the THz range, or equivalently $\sim 1\%$ of the central wavelength) could significantly reduce LPI growth rates by disrupting resonant coupling. However, such bandwidths exceed by more than an order of magnitude those used in fusion-relevant experiments to date and impose major challenges for gain media, frequency-conversion stages, beam-smoothing architectures and overall system design. The development of high-energy, large-bandwidth laser systems, together with advanced

smoothing techniques, is therefore essential to experimentally determine whether broadband illumination can suppress LPI and enhance direct-drive viability.

Milestones

- By 2030, kJ-class laser systems with 0.5–1% bandwidth and advanced beam-smoothing TRL 2-3 strategies should enable experimental studies of laser-plasma-instability mitigation.
- By 2035, broadband fusion-laser architectures and smoothing techniques should mature toward TRL 4-5 to be validated under fusion-relevant interaction conditions.

Challenge II.6 - Advanced optical materials and large-aperture components for IFE

Scaling from present single-shot drivers to laser-fusion power plant imposes demanding requirements on gain materials and optical components, far beyond what current systems can provide. A major challenge is the scaling of high-average-power laser technologies to large apertures, from 15 x 15 cm² (e.g., on DiPOLE) to 40 x 40 cm² (as demonstrated on NIF), as required for multi-MJ-class facilities. While high-thermal-conductivity materials (crystals and ceramics) offer clear advantages for multi-Hz operation, producing them with such apertures (at the meter scale) is well beyond current European industrial capacity. Particular attention should be paid to the compatibility of these materials with the broad spectral bandwidths discussed in the previous challenge, which pose significant challenges for both laser amplification and frequency conversion. In parallel, the resistance of optical materials to laser damage under sustained operation at repetition rates around 10 Hz must be investigated, combining advanced metrology with a deeper understanding of the underlying damage mechanisms. Beyond supporting the European industry to develop the required production capabilities, optical bonding of sub-aperture units and beam-combining architectures provide alternative technical paths.

Milestones

- By 2030, dedicated metrology platforms and physics studies should establish a comprehensive understanding of laser-induced damage mechanisms and bandwidth-related limitations under IFE-relevant operating conditions. Crystalline and ceramic gain materials should demonstrate IFE-relevant performances in terms of aperture size, spectral bandwidth acceptance and durability, reaching TRL 4-5. Optical bonding approaches and initial beam-combining strategies should be demonstrated at relevant energies.
- By 2035, large-aperture crystalline and ceramic materials meeting IFE requirements should progress toward TRL 6–7. Damage-tolerant optical components and assemblies should be qualified for sustained repetitive operation and AI-assisted beam combining validated for high-average-power operation.

Challenge II.7 - Precision Beam Control, Automation and AI for Facility-Scale Operation

Future IFE systems must deliver dozens to hundreds of beams with consistent pointing, wavefront, pulse shape and spectral characteristics, despite thermal drifts, mechanical disturbances and the harsh electromagnetic and radiation environment created by repetitive fusion shots. Manual alignment and operator-driven procedures, still characteristic of current ignition-scale facilities, are incompatible with the multi-Hz operation needed for power-plant-level throughput. Progress requires integrated architectures for predictive stabilization and automated alignment, supported by digital beamline models and fast surrogate models able to manage the coupling between subsystems. Supervision control must orchestrate beam conditioning (including laser-beam zooming, to synchronize the evolution of the laser focal spot with the implosion dynamics), start-up sequences, restart protocols, anomaly detection and health monitoring with minimal human intervention.

Milestones

- By 2030, predictive beam-control architectures combining automated alignment,

stabilization and model-supported supervision control should be validated at TRL 3-4.

- By 2035, facility-scale AI-assisted operation coordinating large beamline arrays should progress to TRL 5-6 to demonstrate reliable repetitive operation with minimal human intervention.

Summary

Laser-driven laser fusion faces formidable challenges, but coordinated advances are still required to unlock a viable pathway toward energy-relevant operation. Europe's leadership in high-intensity laser science and photonics provides a strong foundation, but real progress requires sustained investment and dedicated demonstrators. By the mid-2030s, the combined maturation of high-repetition-rate high-energy broadband lasers, advanced materials and automated facility operation could deliver the first credible prototypes for repetitive fusion-relevant experiments, setting the stage for future pilot-scale IFE facilities and ultimately contributing to a long-term vision of clean, dispatchable fusion power.

III – Industry and manufacturing

Laser-based manufacturing in Europe has demonstrated strong capabilities in ultrafast micromachining, precision surface engineering and additive manufacturing. Yet industrial uptake is still constrained by recurring barriers: processes that work in the lab do not always scale to factory throughput; stability and quality can drift under high repetition rates and harsh environments; and qualification remains costly because too many workflows still rely on empirical tuning and post-process inspection. The key objective for the coming decade is to turn laser manufacturing from “parameter hunting” into a predictable, scalable and certifiable production technology, while improving energy efficiency and reducing waste.

Industry demands ever higher average powers, higher repetition rates and faster motion/handling to increase productivity. In this regime, the underlying physics becomes strongly coupled; heat accumulation, incubation, melt dynamics, phase changes and self-organization, as well as debris ejection, increasingly govern repeatability. But tolerance budgets tighten and acceptable defect levels drop. A cross-cutting approach to resolving this tension is measurement-driven manufacturing: combining high-rate sensing, robust models and real-time decision logic to keep processes stable at industrial cycle times. Data-driven methods (including, where justified, machine-learning components) should be treated as an enabling layer - valuable only insofar as they are validated, latency-aware and qualification-ready.

Lasers are extremely valuable now for their key enabling properties:

- green photonic manufacturing with quantum precision (single pulse control),
- contactless and remote processing,
- no necessary vacuum or cleanroom facilities are necessary,
- suitability for prototyping, mass-customization and parallelized serial 24/7 production.

Challenge III.1 - Scaling laser processing to industrial throughput while maintaining precision and quality

First, industrial throughput can no longer rely solely on power scaling; parallelization and beam shaping (multi-spot/beam-splitting architectures, tailored spatial/temporal energy deposition, high-speed scanning strategies) are now expected to play a key role. Second, quality must be ensured through real-time monitoring of process conditions (thermal load, by-product formation, defect onset) and through process recipes applicable to different representative material classes and surface states (coatings, composites, multi-material stacks).

Milestones

- By 2030, parallelized laser-processing strategies with validated process windows for key material families should reach TRL 5-6 maturity suitable for industrial trials.
- By 2035, factory-scale laser manufacturing platforms, maintaining production-relevant tolerances and repeatable quality at throughput limited primarily by handling and logistics, should become operational at TRL 7-8.

Challenge III.2 – Real-time inline monitoring and closed-loop process control

Inline sensing is only valuable if it prevents defects, not just records them. Industrial relevance requires multimodal diagnostics (coaxial imaging combined with spectral/thermal/plasma proxies where relevant) linked to real-time decision logic. At high throughput, sensing must be pulse-resolved or near-pulse-resolved, with latency-aware data handling that supports drift compensation, adaptive parameters and automatic correction.

Milestones

- By 2030, demonstrated TRL 5-6 capabilities of robust multimodal inline diagnostics, integrated with real-time decision logic, should enable defect detection, drift compensation and adaptive parameter updates, marking a shift from passive monitoring to actionable control.
- By 2035, closed-loop and AI-assisted manufacturing platforms should become available at TRL 7-8 and broadly deployed, sensor fusion feeding qualification-ready data pipelines and digital process twins to support reproducibility and certification-oriented traceability across production sites.

Challenge III.3 – Very-high-repetition-rate, high-average-power, cost-efficient and agile laser systems

Deployable manufacturing requires scalable laser sources optimized not only for peak performance but also for uptime, wall-plug efficiency, long-term stability, predictive maintenance and modularity. Agility in pulse energy, repetition rate, temporal shaping and wavelength becomes essential for adapting to diverse materials and surface states. Industrial packaging and environmental robustness are central enablers.

Milestones

- By 2030, industrial-grade packaging, improved long-term stability and flexible parameter control for next-generation laser systems should be validated at TRL 5-6 to enable reliable integration into production environments.
- By 2035, energy-efficient and robust high-repetition-rate laser platforms should become available at TRL 7-8 for distributed, modular production lines.

Challenge III.4 – Damage-resistant high-numerical-aperture optics and robust beam delivery/shaping

As average powers and beam format complexity increase, contamination, thermal load and long operating hours impact optics durability and beam delivery and, consequently, limit industrial scaling. Qualification of optical lifetime, stability and drift behaviour is thus critical.

Milestones

- By 2030, validated optical toolchains for parallelized processing, including robust beam delivery, standardized beam shaping, lifetime qualification of high-NA optics and drift-aware alignment, should reach TRL 5-6 for industrial deployment.
- By 2035 advanced light management should transition toward TRL 7-8 to enable in situ compensation of thermal and alignment drifts for scalable processing of challenging materials and next-generation substrates.

Challenge III.5 – Renewable/recyclable materials for additive manufacturing and scalable micro-AM routes

Sustainable additive manufacturing requires renewable/recycled feedstocks and robust micro-AM processes with minimal scrap. Achieving this requires co-design of materials, optical fields and qualification strategies. Data-driven approaches can accelerate recipe development but must remain grounded in validated metrology and physical models.

Milestones

- By 2030, renewable and recycled feedstocks should be validated at TRL 5-6 for AM and micro-AM processes that maintain microscale fidelity while reducing scrap and energy consumption.
- By 2035, near-zero-waste AM and reproducible micro-AM at industrial throughput should mature toward TRL 7-8 to enable qualification-ready multi-material and architected components.

Summary

Aligning European efforts around parallelized laser processing, inline sensing and control, robust high-rep-rate laser platforms, damage-resistant optics, and sustainable materials can make laser manufacturing predictable, scalable and certifiable. By 2030–2035, these technologies will enable near-zero-waste additive and subtractive green photonic manufacturing, support advanced semiconductor and substrate processing and unlock architected materials with controlled properties.

IV – Space

The operational space environment is evolving rapidly. The number of active satellites, commercial constellations and orbital debris is increasing, while the needs for reliable monitoring of environmental, strategic and security threats continue to grow. Laser technologies offer unique capabilities for high-precision detection, long-distance tracking and contactless interaction with remote targets, both on Earth and in orbit. However, several scientific and technological barriers still limit large-scale operational deployment, particularly in the areas of propagation physics, environmental resilience and compact high-power laser architectures. Addressing these limitations is essential to support Europe's future space safety, situational awareness and exploration capabilities.

Laser systems provide a set of capabilities that are uniquely suited to the constraints of space operations:

- long-distance, high-precision ranging and tracking, essential for space debris monitoring, satellite navigation and collision avoidance,
- narrow-divergence, high-brightness beams enabling communication, remote sensing and momentum transfer,
- contactless manipulation mechanisms, including radiation pressure and laser ablation, relevant for debris mitigation and small-satellite control,
- high spectral selectivity, supporting chemical, biological and radiological detection from stand-off distances,
- compatibility with spaceborne instrumentation, due to compactness, low mass and fibre-based delivery options,
- 3D mapping and altimetry, enabling planetary exploration, terrain analysis and resource mapping,
- resilience to electromagnetic interference, crucial for harsh space environments.

These capabilities make lasers central to the future of orbital safety, planetary science, space surveillance and deep-space missions. In addition, many of the involved technologies are inherently dual-use, supporting both civilian and security-oriented space capabilities

Challenge IV.1 - AI-assisted atmospheric correction and optical event discrimination

Reliable long-distance laser propagation and accurate detection of remote targets require advanced correction of atmospheric turbulence, thermal blooming and wavefront distortion. Adaptive optics must be combined with data-driven correction algorithms capable of operating at high speed and discriminating true events from complex background signals in large-scale space surveillance networks.

Milestones

- By 2030, integrated adaptive-optics platforms combining high-speed wavefront sensing and validated AI-assisted correction methods should demonstrate TRL 4-5 capabilities for reliable long-distance laser propagation and improved space-object tracking.
- By 2035, systems capable of autonomous atmospheric correction and real-time event discrimination should reach TRL 6-7 for deployment within continental-scale optical surveillance infrastructures.

Challenge IV.2 - Radiation-hardening of space-compatible optical components

Spaceborne optical systems must operate reliably over long mission durations despite exposure to radiation, contamination, extreme temperatures and vacuum-induced degradation. Understanding radiation-induced changes in coatings, substrates and sources and developing robust qualification procedures linking laboratory tests to orbital conditions, are essential for dependable high-power systems in space.

Milestones

- By 2030, radiation-resistant optical materials and coatings should be validated at TRL 5-6 for long-duration missions, supported by qualification methods bridging laboratory and orbital environments.
- By 2035, a new generation of fully space-qualified optical components should mature toward TRL 7-8 to enable reliable high-power laser operation on orbit and on planetary missions.

Challenge IV.3 - Miniaturized high-average-power laser sources with adaptive beam control

Space applications require compact, efficient and thermally managed laser systems capable of delivering high beam quality with narrow divergence. Such systems must integrate precise steering, adaptive optics and radiation-tolerant control electronics within strict mass and power budgets.

Milestones

- By 2030, compact laser architectures combining high average power, effective thermal management and precision beam steering should demonstrate TRL 4-5 capabilities and compatibility with both ground-based and spaceborne platforms.
- By 2035, these technologies should establish scalable laser infrastructures at TRL 6-7 for space situational awareness, planetary mapping and advanced remote sensing missions.

Summary

If these technological priorities are achieved, lasers will play a transformative role in Europe's space capabilities. High-precision sensing and tracking systems could significantly enhance orbital safety by improving detection of debris and reducing collision risk. Laser-based momentum transfer techniques may contribute to future debris-removal strategies and the

sustainable use of orbital infrastructure. Laser-enabled spectroscopic detection could strengthen global security by identifying hazardous substances from stand-off distances. In planetary exploration, laser instruments would support surface composition analysis, atmospheric characterization and resource mapping. Coordinated progress in adaptive beam control, radiation-resistant optical materials and compact high-power laser sources will enable Europe to translate fundamental laser science into operational systems supporting space safety, global monitoring and exploration missions across the 2030–2045 horizon.

V – Security

Security and defence environments are becoming increasingly complex, from evolving threat landscapes to rapid advances in unmanned systems, remote sensing and secure communications. Laser technologies provide unique capabilities for precision sensing, stand-off detection of hazardous materials, secure communication links and emerging directed-energy applications. Europe already holds strong positions in photonics and spectroscopy, but the translation of high-performance laboratory systems into robust, operationally deployable technologies remains limited. The strategic objective for 2030–2035 is to deliver reliable, field-ready laser-based sensing and communication tools that operate in variable, dynamic and often harsh environments.

Lasers enable capabilities that are essential for next-generation security and safety systems:

- high-sensitivity, stand-off spectroscopic detection of explosives, chemical agents and hazardous materials,
- high-resolution LiDAR for terrain mapping, change detection and aerosol/bio-agent monitoring (strong link to the Environment roadmap),
- secure, high-bandwidth laser communications, resistant to RF interference and jamming (cross-linking Communications & Computing),
- precise, narrow-divergence beams enabling discrimination, tracking and low-false-alarm sensing,
- pulsed and ultrafast sources allowing chemical fingerprinting, fluorescence-based bio-detection and remote Raman analysis,
- compact, rugged architectures, enabling mobile, drone-borne or distributed deployment.

These capabilities position lasers as critical assets for next-generation situational awareness, threat detection and secure information exchange. Progress also depends on photonic integration and low-SWaP laser architectures compatible with portable, vehicle-mounted and drone-borne systems.

Challenge V.1 — Stand-off laser-based detection of explosives and hazardous substances

Stand-off identification of hazardous materials requires sensitive, selective and interference-robust spectroscopy. Real-world conditions (mixed substrates, concealment, variable illumination, dust, humidity) often distort signatures and degrade reliability. Progress depends on combining complementary spectroscopic methods (Raman, LIF, IR absorption, LIBS), improved physical models of signal formation and validated data interpretation pipelines.

Milestones

- By 2030, deployable multimodal spectroscopic platforms should demonstrate, at TRL 4-5, quantified detection limits and controlled false-alarm rates in realistic environments for detection and identification of key classes of hazardous substances.

- By 2035, standardized stand-off sensing platforms integrating Raman, LIBS, LIF and IR spectroscopy should progress toward TRL 6-7 to support reliable hazardous-material detection in operational environments

Challenge V.2 — Reliable identification within complex and variable backgrounds

Operational environments often contain mixtures of interfering compounds, complex surfaces and changing atmospheric conditions. Achieving robust distinction between threat and non-threat signatures requires multi-modal sensing and advanced classification strategies capable of handling uncertainty.

Milestones

- By 2030, multimodal sensing combined with advanced classification algorithms should be upgraded to TRL 4-5 for robust identification under variable and uncertain conditions.
- By 2035, integrated sensing and classification platforms should achieve TRL 6-7 for high-confidence threat identification in complex operational scenarios with minimized false alarms.

Challenge V.3 — System integration, mobility and operational usability

For real-world adoption, laser-based security technologies must be compact, rugged, low-maintenance and deployable on mobile platforms. They must operate reliably under broad temperature, humidity, dust and vibration conditions and be usable by non-specialists.

Milestones

- By 2030, compact ruggedized photonic sensing platforms with simplified calibration and user interfaces should, at TRL 5-6, support mobile and distributed deployment.
- By 2035, autonomous laser-based sensing systems with low-maintenance operation should become deployable at TRL 7-8 to be integrated seamlessly into large-scale surveillance infrastructures for continuous or on-demand monitoring.

Summary

Laser technologies have the potential to significantly strengthen Europe's security capabilities over the coming decades. Stand-off detection systems could enable rapid identification of explosives, chemical agents and hazardous materials in critical environments. High-resolution LiDAR could enhance situational awareness through precise 3D mapping and aerosol/biological threat monitoring. Secure optical communication could support jamming-resistant information exchange in contested environments. Coordinated progress in sensing, system integration and autonomous operation will allow Europe to transition from high-performance laboratory techniques to trusted, operational systems delivering reliable information under real-world conditions.

VI – Communications and computing

Laser-based technologies underpin modern communications, photonic integration and advanced component manufacturing. Europe has world-leading capabilities across the value chain, from ultrafast laser sources and optical materials to semiconductor manufacturing and lithography and plays a central role in global photonics standards. Yet next-generation communication and computing systems will require a new class of optical components operating in the visible and near-IR, with nanometric precision, low loss and seamless integration with electronics. Achieving this transition demands progress in short-wavelength laser sources, high-resolution manufacturing methods, advanced materials and heterogeneous photonic/CMOS integration. Between 2030 and 2035, the strategic goal is to establish scalable, high-resolution and fully integrated photonic–optoelectronic platforms

enabling post-CMOS information processing, high-performance optical computing and secure communication networks.

Lasers enable capabilities that are essential for next-generation photonics and computing:

- sub-wavelength material modification using ultrashort pulses, HHG-driven XUV/EUV beams and self-organized nano-structuring,
- nanometric precision and low thermal load, suitable for optical components operating in VIS/near-IR,
- 3D tailoring of refractive index and polarization, enabling compact waveguides, tuneable elements and integrated light sources,
- high-flux short-wavelength generation for lithography, nanofabrication and metrology,
- heterogeneous integration of active and passive photonic components with CMOS electronics,
- coherent light-field control for emerging petahertz optoelectronics,
- scalability toward wafer-level processes, supporting manufacturing routes borrowed from semiconductor technology.

These capabilities make lasers not only fabrication tools but also enablers for advanced communication, computing and quantum-information systems.

Challenge VI.1 – Extending laser-based manufacturing to high-performance VIS/near-IR optical components

Laser manufacturing is well established in the mid-IR and THz, but VIS/near-IR photonics demands resolutions beyond the diffraction limit of conventional processing. Three complementary routes are emerging: (i) the use of VUV/XUV/EUV ultrashort-pulse sources for surface structuring below 10 nm, (ii) new optical materials supporting self-organized nanostructures for diffraction/polarization control and (iii) hybrid additive–subtractive processes similar to semiconductor manufacturing. These must converge with improved beam management, XUV-compatible optics and integration of microcrystal laser structures (e.g., perovskite microwires).

Milestones

- By 2030, advanced laser-fabrication strategies combining nanometric resolution and low optical losses should be demonstrated at TRL 3-4 for key VIS/near-IR photonic components.
- By 2035, scalable laser-based fabrication of sub-10 nm low-loss photonic structures should progress toward TRL 5-6 to enable highly integrated VIS/near-IR optical platforms.

Challenge VI.2 - High-flux, well-controlled short-wavelength (XUV/EUV) sources

Next-generation nanofabrication, lithography, spectroscopy and metrology require stable, high-flux XUV/EUV beams. Progress relies on high-average-power mJ-class lasers at MHz repetition rates, improved HHG efficiency and fine control of the driving field (CEP control, multi-colour driving). Narrowband harmonic selection via multilayer mirrors and gratings will support high-precision processing.

Milestones

- By 2030, high-repetition-rate HHG-based XUV/EUV sources with improved flux, spectral selectivity and stability should reach TRL 4-5 to support nanoscale fabrication and metrology.
- By 2035, high-flux XUV/EUV sources should mature to TRL 5-6 to be deployed for few-nm manufacturing and advanced photonic-device engineering.

Challenge VI.3 - Integration of photonic and electronic subsystems

Current photonic devices often require separate manufacturing of optical and electronic elements. Laser-based XUV/EUV processing and advanced lithography offer a pathway toward unified, CMOS-compatible photonic/electronic platforms. As XUV/EUV tools become more accessible, they may democratize semiconductor-class fabrication for research labs and SMEs, enabling hybrid devices with increased complexity, reduced footprint and improved performance.

Milestones

- By 2030, CMOS-compatible laser-based fabrication platforms at TRL 4-5 should support intermediate-scale heterogeneous photonic/electronic integration.
- By 2035, highly integrated heterogeneous photonic/CMOS architectures should become operational at TRL 6-7, enabling compact advanced communication and computing systems.

Challenge VI.4 - Advanced photonic and optoelectronic functionalities at the device and system level

Future communication and computing systems will rely on miniaturized, tuneable, low-noise on-chip lasers, materials enabling PHz light-field-driven operation, preservation of coherence, phase and polarization across complex circuits, reliable cascading of ultrafast optical functionalities and scalable architectures enabling readout and reversible dynamics.

Achieving this requires breakthroughs in gain materials, nonlinear materials, integrated photonics and advanced measurement strategies (optical field sampling, attosecond transient absorption, photoemission spectroscopy).

Milestones

- By 2030, integrated photonic platforms combining low-noise on-chip laser sources, coherent light control and proof of principle functionalities should be demonstrated at TRL 2-3.
- By 2035, scalable optoelectronic systems should be pushed to TRL 4-5 to support secure quantum communications, high-performance optical computing and early PHz-class information-processing systems.

Summary

If Europe advances along these priorities (high-resolution laser-based fabrication, high-flux short-wavelength sources, heterogeneous photonic/CMOS integration, and coherent ultrafast optoelectronics), laser technologies will underpin next-generation communication and computing. Between 2030 and 2045, they could enable low-loss photonic circuits, high-speed secure communication networks, modular optical computing and the first practical implementations of petahertz information-processing technologies. Strengthening Europe's leadership will require coordinated progress in laser science, lithography, materials and system-level integration.

VII – Environment, Climate and Agrifood

Environment, climate and agrifood systems face tightly interlinked pressures. Rising concentrations of greenhouse gases, increasing frequency of floods, droughts and wildfires and persistent pollution present urgent challenges. Food security must be ensured for a growing global population under constraints of water scarcity, soil degradation and reduced fertilizer and pesticide use, while ensuring safety from toxins, microplastics and chemical contaminants. Europe also needs improved strategies for waste reduction, recycling and recovery of critical raw materials.

Laser-based technologies already play a central role in addressing these challenges. They support atmospheric sensing, trace gas detection, remote mapping, waste sorting, precision agriculture and food safety. Europe has world-leading expertise in high-resolution spectroscopy and remote sensing, yet broad deployment requires transitioning from laboratory-grade instruments to robust, autonomous, distributed sensing systems. Between now and 2035, the key objective is to establish reliable, field-ready laser-based platforms delivering continuous, actionable data across environmental, agricultural and industrial settings.

Laser systems provide capabilities essential for next-generation environmental and agrifood monitoring:

- high-sensitivity spectroscopic detection of trace gases, pollutants, nutrients and contaminants,
- selective, species-specific identification even in chemically complex environments,
- remote, stand-off and airborne sensing, supporting large-area monitoring,
- 3D mapping via LIDAR, enabling forest inventory, biodiversity tracking and carbon stock estimation,
- chemical and biological analysis in soils, crops, water and food chains,
- non-contact inspection, valuable for contamination-free monitoring,
- compatibility with distributed and mobile platforms (drones, vehicles, fixed stations),
- fast, continuous operation, supporting early-warning systems and real-time decision frameworks.

These strengths make lasers a cornerstone technology for environmental intelligence, precision agriculture and resource-efficient production. As for Security, progress depends on photonic integration and low-SWaP laser architectures, as well as energy-efficient operation compatible with large distributed sensing networks.

Challenge VII.1 - Laser-based sensing for multi-species, sensitive and selective detection in complex environments

Laser-based spectroscopy can reach extremely low detection limits under controlled laboratory conditions, but performance often degrades in real-world settings due to interfering species, background variability and heterogeneous media. Achieving reliable operation in the atmosphere, soils, crops, waste streams, or food products requires robust multi-species detection strategies combining advanced laser spectroscopy, physics-based models, multivariate analysis and validated machine-learning components. Progress depends on improved understanding of light propagation in heterogeneous environments, background signatures, atmospheric effects and interacting signals.

The goal is to develop compact, energy-efficient, multi-species sensors capable of delivering validated measurements across diverse conditions, from greenhouse gas monitoring to plant stress detection, pollutant tracking, agrifood inspection and waste sorting.

Milestones

- By 2030, field-deployable multi-species laser sensing platforms with validated sensitivity and selectivity should demonstrate TRL 4-5 capabilities to support mobile and distributed environmental, agrifood and food-safety monitoring.
- By 2035, interoperable distributed sensing networks, using standardized data formats, should reach TRL 6-7 to enable continuous monitoring at local-regional-global scales.

Challenge VII.2 - Instrumentation robustness, portability and autonomous operation

To operate outside controlled laboratory conditions, laser-based monitoring systems must tolerate harsh environments, mechanical stress, variable weather, dust, humidity and temperature extremes. They must also require minimal maintenance or calibration, operate with high energy efficiency and integrate seamlessly into distributed monitoring infrastructures.

Autonomous operation, including self-diagnostics, remote control and long-term stability, is essential for widespread field deployment.

Designing such systems requires early integration of ruggedization, stability, low-power operation, environmental sealing, contamination tolerance, drift management and calibration-free or calibration-light architectures.

Milestones

- By 2030, ruggedized, low-power autonomous laser instruments, with reduced calibration requirements, should be validated at TRL 5-6 to support initial large-scale field deployment.
- By 2035, fully autonomous, long-duration sensing platforms requiring minimal human intervention should become deployable at TRL 7-8 and integrate into regional and continental environmental monitoring infrastructures.

Summary

If Europe aligns around these priorities (robust multi-species sensing, improved understanding of light-matter interaction in complex environments, enhanced chemical and biological specificity, and rugged field-ready systems), laser-based technologies can deliver transformative impact across climate, biodiversity, agrifood and resource management. Between 2030 and 2045, reliable laser-enabled monitoring networks will support greenhouse gas mitigation strategies, enable precision agriculture with optimized resource use, enhance food safety and contamination control and improve waste recycling and raw-material recovery. The path to broad impact requires scaling high-performance laboratory techniques into distributed, interoperable, qualification-ready sensing infrastructures.

VIII – Cultural Heritage

Europe's cultural heritage is increasingly threatened by environmental stressors, material ageing, structural instability and the often-unpredictable behaviour of modern materials. Objects and monuments, typically composed of complex and heterogeneous combinations of organic and inorganic components, require diagnostic and conservation methods that are non-invasive, high-resolution and sensitive to chemical and structural changes. Laser-based and photonic technologies already offer unique capabilities for such tasks, yet their deployment remains uneven, limited by technological barriers, lack of standardization and the need for specialized expertise.

Europe has the opportunity to build an interoperable ecosystem of advanced laser-based tools, data-driven analysis methods and portable platforms that can be used across museums, archaeological sites, laboratories and conservation studios. Such an ecosystem would strengthen preventive conservation, enable safer interventions and support long-term preservation at scale.

Heritage materials degrade via chemical, mechanical and photochemical processes that evolve over timescales ranging from milliseconds to decades. Their layered structure and inherent heterogeneity make them difficult to analyse with conventional methods. Laser-based technologies uniquely combine:

- non-invasive probing of chemical composition, morphology and microstructure,
- high spatial resolution, enabling examination of microscale inhomogeneities,
- depth-resolved analysis of stratified paintings, coatings, corrosion layers and deposits,
- selective, controlled material interaction, enabling precise cleaning or surface modification,
- portability, allowing diagnostics to take place directly on artworks and monuments.

Their ability to unify structural, chemical and functional information, while minimizing risk to the object, makes lasers a foundational technology for modern cultural heritage science.

Challenge VIII.1 - Advanced high-resolution diagnostic techniques and multimodal platforms

Cultural heritage materials demand analytical approaches that can resolve complex, multi-layered and chemically diverse structures without sampling. Progress depends on the coordinated integration of complementary laser-based methods (Raman spectroscopy, LIBS, nonlinear optical microscopy, photoacoustic imaging, fluorescence and FLIM and infrared spectroscopy) to achieve high spatial resolution, enhanced chemical specificity and depth-profiling. Developing interoperable multimodal platforms, equipped with standardized protocols and supported by AI-driven data fusion and automated interpretation, is essential for producing reliable and scalable diagnostics suitable for both experts and non-specialists.

Milestones

- By 2030, interoperable multimodal, high-resolution and non-invasive, laser-diagnostic platforms with validated protocols should reach TRL 4-5 to support analysis of complex, multi-layered and heterogeneous heritage materials.
- By 2035, AI-assisted multimodal diagnostic systems enabling real-time data fusion and automated interpretation should become routinely available at TRL 6-7.

Challenge VIII.2 - Portable and in situ laser systems

Many heritage objects and monuments cannot be moved and their composition evolves under real environmental conditions. Reliable, high-quality in situ diagnostics therefore require portable and ruggedized laser systems with intuitive interfaces, efficient detection modules and connectivity to remote expertise. Miniaturization of laser sources, user-centred instrument design and seamless integration with cloud-enabled processing pipelines will allow advanced analytics to be deployed directly in museums, archives and archaeological sites. Such systems should operate as nodes in a distributed European network for large-scale monitoring and preventive conservation.

Milestones

- By 2030, portable high-performance laser diagnostics systems should be validated at TRL 5-6 and enable real-time, in situ assessments of degradation processes.
- By 2035, networked in-situ monitoring platforms should reach TRL 7-8 for large-scale, distributed assessment of heritage assets.

Challenge VIII.3 – Safe laser-based conservation and restoration technologies

The safe use of lasers in conservation relies on a precise understanding of laser–material interactions and well-defined operating windows. Photothermal, photochemical or mechanical effects can be beneficial or harmful depending on material sensitivity, fluence, wavelength and pulse duration. Establishing reference databases of material-specific thresholds, standardized protocols for safe operation and validated procedures for inherently micro-destructive methods such as LIBS is crucial. At the same time, conservation treatments will benefit from advances in adaptive, feedback-controlled laser systems capable of selective cleaning, layer-by-layer removal and real-time monitoring, enabling reproducible and minimally invasive interventions.

Milestones

- By 2030, validated protocols defining safe laser–material interaction conditions should be established at TRL 5-6.
- By 2035, standards for safe laser-based conservation procedures and deployment of adaptive, feedback-controlled treatment systems should be widely implemented at TRL 7-8.

Summary

Laser-based technologies will become a cornerstone of Europe's cultural heritage strategy, enabling deeper understanding, more precise diagnostics and safer, more effective conservation interventions. Their combination with data science, standardized protocols and interoperable platforms will support a unified European ecosystem linking research infrastructures, museums, archives, archaeological sites and industry. By 2035, this integrated approach is expected to deliver robust, scalable and widely accessible tools for the preservation of artworks, monuments and historical collections. It will strengthen Europe's global leadership in heritage science and ensure that its cultural assets can be monitored, understood and safeguarded for future generations.

IX – Science at the extremes

Science at the extremes explores the highest intensities, shortest timescales and most nonlinear regimes of light-matter interaction. It spans strong-field quantum electrodynamics, relativistic plasma physics, attosecond and deep-UV science, ultrafast dynamics in quantum materials, precision metrology and emerging quantum technologies. Progress in these fields is inseparable from progress in laser technology: peak power, stability, spectral coverage, timing precision and quantum control define the boundary of what is experimentally accessible. Over the next decade, advances in ultrafast and extreme-intensity laser systems will push the limits of both fundamental science and cutting-edge applications.

Exploring ultrafast and extreme regimes requires light sources that combine:

- multi-PW peak intensity with ultra-high temporal contrast,
- few-cycle and as pulses at high repetition rates,
- tunability from mid-IR and deep-UV to XUV and soft X-rays,
- high-photon-flux as sources for complex materials,
- non-classical light generation for quantum-enhanced probes,
- tailored waveforms and structured light for advanced control,
- CEP-stabilized drivers for sub-cycle physics,
- zeptosecond-scale timing and synchronization,
- damage-resistant optics capable of withstanding extreme fluences.

These capabilities determine the frontiers of relativistic, ultrafast and quantum physics.

Challenge IX.1 - Ultrafast laser sources for strong-field and Schwinger-regime physics

Reaching strong-field QED requires intensities several orders of magnitude above today's capabilities. Electron-assisted Schwinger experiments, combining multi-PW lasers with GeV-class laser-plasma-accelerated electrons, offer a practical route by boosting the field in the electron rest frame. An alternative uses relativistic plasma mirrors for extreme field compression, requiring single-cycle pulses with unprecedented temporal contrast. These experiments demand multi-PW beamlines with femtosecond synchronization, precise control over electron-laser collision geometry and diagnostics for nonlinear Compton scattering, radiation reaction and pair production.

Milestones

- By 2030, synchronized multi-PW laser and relativistic electron beams should reach TRL 2-3 to pave the way for first systematic strong-field QED studies, while relativistic plasma mirrors should allow multi-order field enhancement.
- by 2035, near-Schwinger-regime laser platforms with advanced field-compression and synchronization TRL 4-5 capabilities should support exploration of nonlinear vacuum phenomena.

Challenge IX.2 - High-repetition-rate, high-average-power few-cycle laser drivers

Future ultrafast science requires few-femtosecond pulses delivered at MHz rates and high average power. Progress in OPCPA, fibre-based post-compression and multi-pass cells is enabling multi-GW peak powers at high repetition rates. The emergence of GHz repetition-rate chip-scale comb sources will support broadband metrology and advanced frequency-domain spectroscopy. These systems will drive next-generation attosecond sources, ultrafast electronics and control of functional quantum materials.

Milestones

- By 2030, GHz chip-scale combs should be integrated as coherent front ends in scalable ultrafast sources and multi-GW few-cycle drivers at MHz repetition rates emerge at TRL 3-4.
- By 2035, compact high-average-power few-cycle drivers should become operational at TRL 5-6 to be widely deployed for field-resolved and attosecond spectroscopy and ultrafast laser control should be routinely used in quantum materials and ultrafast electronic devices.

Challenge IX.3 - Few-cycle high-power deep-UV laser sources

Deep-UV pulses with few-femtosecond duration enable access to electronic dynamics in photochemistry, biophysics and materials science. Advances in resonant dispersive-wave emission, hollow-core fibres and nonlinear up-conversion in gases are crucial for generating tuneable deep-UV pulses with high temporal coherence. Future development will focus on polarization control, long-term stability and enhanced quantum efficiency. These improvements will ultimately support attosecond pulse generation in the deep UV.

Milestones

- By 2030, engineered resonant dispersive wave emission and coherent pulse synthesis should provide, at TRL 2-3, tuneable few-fs deep-UV pulses.
- By 2035, direct attosecond pulse generation in the deep-UV range should allow, at TRL 4-5, real-time photochemical and biomolecular studies.

Challenge IX.4 - High-photon-flux attosecond sources, attosecond quantum optics and non-classical light

Attosecond science is transitioning from highly specialized laboratories to broader experimental environments, requiring higher photon flux, higher repetition rates and improved stability. High-order harmonic generation driven by long-wavelength lasers, advanced quasi-phase matching and MHz-rate pumping will produce XUV/soft-X-ray fluxes approaching free-electron laser levels. In parallel, a new frontier, attosecond quantum optics, aims to manipulate strong-field emission with squeezed or entangled states, reduce quantum noise in attosecond metrology and probe quantum-field behaviour under extreme conditions.

Milestones

- By 2030, harmonic sources exceeding 10^{15} photons/s in the XUV at ≥ 100 kHz should be validated at TRL 3 to support attosecond spectroscopy of complex environments (liquids, surfaces, interfaces, nanomaterials) and first demonstrations of non-classical-light effects in HHG or strong-field emission might be achieved.
- By 2035, high-repetition-rate soft-X-ray attosecond probes, matured toward TRL 4, should be used for multidimensional ultrafast spectroscopy, while quantum-enhanced attosecond metrology would allow reducing noise and improving sensitivity to lay foundations for quantum-enabled extreme-field sensing and ultrafast quantum information protocols.

Challenge IX.5 - High-damage-threshold optics for extreme intensities

Multi-PW and extreme-intensity systems require optical materials capable of surviving ultrafast excitation, plasma formation and lattice heating. Understanding sub-cycle absorption processes (electron excitation, plasmonic heating, and ultrafast defect formation) is essential

for designing coatings with high homogeneity, low absorption and tailored nonlinear response. Progress in ultrafast characterization will guide the development of next-generation optics.

Milestones

- By 2030, sub-cycle absorption mechanisms should be characterized in next-generation dielectric and metallic coatings.
- By 2035, broadband, high-damage-threshold optics should reach TRL 5-6 and be deployed to enable sustained operation of multi-PW laser systems.

Challenge IX.6 - Advanced light shaping and manipulation technologies

Structured beams (vortex modes, vector beams, chiral fields, optical skyrmions) enable new degrees of control in ultrafast and quantum experiments. Achieving this at high intensities requires broadband, damage-resistant optical components, high-power spatial light modulators and meta-optic devices capable of controlling phase, amplitude and polarization with subwavelength precision. AI-driven wavefront optimization will refine beam profiles for nanoscale fabrication, microscopy and quantum information.

Milestones

- By 2030, broadband meta-optic components and AI-optimized structured illumination would be expected to, at TRL 2-3, support quantum protocols.
- By 2035, high-power structured-light systems, progressing toward TRL 4-5, could enable topological light states, 3D chiral shaping and advanced information-processing schemes.

Challenge IX.7 - Waveform and carrier-envelope phase Control

CEP and waveform control determine the precise electric field driving strong-field and attosecond processes. Achieving shot-to-shot stability at MHz repetition rates requires advances in OPCPA phase stabilization, CEP locking based on difference-frequency generation and solid-state CEP detection. Spatially resolved CEP mapping will enable multidimensional control of attosecond pulse formation and sub-cycle manipulation.

Milestones

- By 2030, shot-to-shot CEP stabilization at MHz repetition rates, along with spatially resolved single-shot CEP detection, would likely be demonstrated at TRL 3-4 in integrated ultrafast systems.
- By 2035, fully stabilized waveform control should mature toward TRL 5-6 to support sub-cycle manipulation of electron dynamics and quantum processes.

Challenge IX.8 - Timing technologies and high temporal resolution

Laser-driven experiments increasingly require synchronization at the attosecond and eventually zeptosecond, level. Advances beyond piezoelectric control will be needed, including comb-to-comb locking, phase-stable frequency synthesis and optical timing networks. Such precision will underpin relativistic electron-laser collisions, multidimensional attosecond pump-probe studies and ultra-precise metrology.

Milestones

- By 2030, attosecond-level synchronization between independent ultrafast laser systems should become achievable at TRL 2-3.
- By 2035, timing accuracy should approach TRL 4 and the zeptosecond regime for next-generation extreme-field and quantum-dynamic experiments.

Summary

Progress across these challenges will fundamentally expand the reach of ultrafast and extreme-intensity science. Multi-PW synchronized drivers, high-photon-flux attosecond probes, quantum-enhanced light sources, deep-UV attosecond pulses, meta-optic beam shaping,

CEP-controlled waveforms, and zeptosecond timing will unlock access to new physical regimes, from strong-field QED and relativistic plasma physics to quantum materials, attosecond chemistry, and ultrafast quantum information. These technologies will also support transformative applications in industry, including semiconductor metrology, advanced materials processing, ultrafast electronics, chemical synthesis, and clean-energy concepts such as laser-inertial fusion. Coordinated developments across academia, national laboratories and industry will be essential for bringing these capabilities to operational maturity by the mid-2030s.

Outlook

The challenges described throughout this roadmap reveal a rapidly converging technological ecosystem in which advances in laser science increasingly generate impact across multiple societal and industrial domains.

Cross-Cutting Technological Priorities and Strategic Convergence

While the roadmap is structured around major societal, industrial and scientific application domains, the analysis conducted throughout this exercise highlights the strong convergence of technological needs across them. Many challenges that appear application-specific are in fact rooted in a limited number of common technological building blocks whose maturation would benefit multiple sectors simultaneously.

Advanced laser primary and secondary laser sources

Progress across health, clean energy, manufacturing, communications, space and science at the extremes relies on the development of compact, efficient, high-repetition-rate laser systems that combine improved stability, tunability, scalability and temporal / spectral control. Depending on the application, requirements range from MHz few-cycle ultrafast systems and compact fibre-based architectures to multi-kJ and multi-PW drivers. Advances in wall-plug efficiency, thermal management, environmental robustness and long-term stability therefore constitute a foundational priority across the entire roadmap.

The roadmap also underscores the rising importance of laser-driven secondary sources: compact electron and ion accelerators, ultrafast X-ray sources, and attosecond probes. These enabling tools cut across medicine, materials science, fusion research, communications/metrology and ultrafast physics. Their development demands coordinated progress in high-power laser technologies, target engineering, synchronization and high-damage-threshold optics.

Advanced diagnostics, sensing and instrumentation

Many domains require increasingly sophisticated multimodal optical platforms that operate in real-world environments while delivering quantitative, high-resolution and often real-time information. This includes medical imaging and spectroscopy, industrial inline diagnostics, environmental monitoring, stand-off security sensing, cultural heritage analysis and ultrafast scientific instrumentation. Common needs emerge in ultrafast detection, multimodal data fusion, AI-assisted interpretation, calibration/traceability, portability and autonomous operation.

Laser-assisted manufacturing, materials engineering and optical component technologies

High-precision laser additive and subtractive processing, advanced coatings, structured surfaces, radiation-hard materials and damage-resistant optics are required across domains, from clean energy and industrial manufacturing to communications, fusion and extreme-intensity science. Key bottlenecks remain scalability, reproducibility, qualification and compatibility with industrial environments remain key bottlenecks. Progress in high-throughput

laser manufacturing, beam shaping/parallelization, optical lifetime and drift qualification and advanced materials processing will have broad system-level impact.

Integration of increasingly complex systems and infrastructures

Future laser-enabled technologies depend not only on components, but also on integrating sources, diagnostics, data pipelines, AI-assisted control, and autonomous decision systems into coherent operational platforms. This applies to clinical photonics, industrial production lines, distributed sensing networks, space systems and next-generation photonic computing. Digital twins, interoperable standards, predictive control and AI-assisted supervision systems and cybersecurity-aware architectures will be essential for scalability and operational reliability.

Taken together, these cross-cutting technological priorities show that progress in laser science and technology increasingly hinges on coordinated developments that span multiple application domains. Strengthening synergies between communities, research infrastructures, industrial actors, and European programs will be essential to accelerate innovation, avoid fragmentation, and maximize strategic impact of future investments. Rather than a collection of independent sectoral roadmaps, this document highlights a highly interconnected technological ecosystem in which advances in one domain can catalyse transformative benefits across many others.

Glossary

Orders of magnitude

- Time: zeptosecond (zs - 10^{-21} s), attosecond (as - 10^{-18} s), femtosecond (fs - 10^{-15} s), picosecond (ps - 10^{-12} s), nanosecond (ns - 10^{-9} s)
- Frequency: megahertz (MHz - 10^6 Hz), gigahertz (GHz - 10^9 Hz), terahertz (THz - 10^{12} Hz), petahertz (PHz - 10^{15} Hz)
- Energy & Power: millijoule (mJ - 10^{-3} J), kilojoule (kJ - 10^3 J), megajoule (MJ - 10^6 J), megawatt (MW - 10^6 W), mega-electron-volt (MeV - 10^6 eV), gigawatt (GW - 10^9 W), giga-electron-volt (GeV - 10^9 eV), terawatt (TW - 10^{12} W), petawatt (PW - 10^{15} W)
- Length: nanometre (nm - 10^{-9} m)

Abbreviations

- 2D & 3D: bi-dimensional and tri-dimensional
- AI: artificial intelligence
- AM: additive manufacturing
- CEP: carrier-envelope phase
- CMOS: complementary metal oxide semiconductor
- CT: computed tomography
- DT: deuterium-tritium
- EUV: extreme ultraviolet (engineering)
- FLIM: fluorescence lifetime imaging microscopy
- HHG: high-order harmonic generation
- ICF: inertial confinement fusion
- IFE: inertial fusion for energy
- IR: infrared
- LIBS: laser-induced breakdown spectroscopy
- LIDAR: light detection and ranging
- LIF: laser-induced fluorescence
- LIFT: laser-induced forward transfer
- LIPSS: laser-induced periodic surface structures
- LPI: laser-plasma interaction
- MDR: medical device regulation
- NA: numerical aperture
- NIF: National Ignition Facility
- OCT: optical coherence tomography
- OPCPA: optical parametric chirped-pulse amplification
- PET: positron emission tomography
- PLD: pulse laser deposition
- QED: quantum electrodynamics
- R&D: research and development
- SFG: sum frequency generation
- SME: small and medium enterprise
- SWaP: size, weight and power
- Ti: titanium
- TRL: technology readiness level
- UV: ultraviolet
- VIS: visible
- VUV: vacuum ultraviolet
- XUV: extreme ultraviolet (physics & optics)
- YAG: yttrium aluminium garnet
- Yb: ytterbium

Composition of the Scientific Writing Group

This roadmap reflects the collective work of many contributors whose scientific expertise, constructive discussions and strategic perspectives have been invaluable. Their engagement, insight and shared commitment to advancing laser science and technology have been essential throughout the development of this document.

Jacquemot, Sylvie

LULI (France)

Anglos, Dimitrios

FORTH (Greece)

Arnaut, Luis

U. Coimbra (Portugal)

Bagnoud, Vincent

GSI (Germany)

Calegari, Francesca

DESY (Germany)

Cerullo, Giulio

POLIMI (Italy)

Cicchi, Riccardo

LENS (Italy)

Consoli, Fabrizio

ENEA (Italy)

Giakoumaki, Anastasia

FORTH (Greece)

Hanus, Václav

HUN-REN Wigner RCP (Hungary)

Hauschwitz, Petr

HiLASE (Czechia)

Loukakos, Panos

FORTH (Greece)

Malinauskas, Mangirdas

VULRC (Lithuania)

Metzges-Ng, Josephine

HZDR (Germany)

Mevel, Eric

CELIA (France)

Mosca, Sara

STFC/RAL (United Kingdom)

Neauport, Jérôme

CEA/CESTA (France)

Petit, Stéphane

CELIA (France)

Popescu andrei

INFLPR (Romania)

Popp, Jürgen

Leibniz-IPHT (Germany)

Romero, Rosa

Sphere Photonics (Portugal)

Samartzis, Petros

FORTH (Greece)

Simon-Boisson, Christophe

Thales LAS (France)

Trabattoni andrea

DESY (Germany)

Vanda, Jan

HiLASE (Czechia)

Vengris, Mikas

VULC (Lithuania)

Wojtanowski, Jacek

WAT (Poland)

Zyla, Gordon

VULRC (Lithuania)

LASERLAB-EUROPE AISBL

Laserlab-Europe AISBL is an international not-for-profit association bringing together 48 leading laser research infrastructures across 22 European countries. Its members provide leadership in laser-based and photonics research, as well as in related enabling technologies, by offering world-class experimental capabilities, user-oriented services and a strong commitment to training the next generation of researchers and engineers.

Laserlab-Europe is built on a long-standing tradition of European collaboration. Its roots trace back to early EU networking initiatives in the 1990s, which laid the foundation for coordinated laser research beyond national borders. This cooperation became more structured with the EU-funded project, Laserlab-Europe I (2004–2008), which united 17 infrastructures from nine countries and established the groundwork for what was envisioned as a unified “European Distributed Laser Infrastructure”. Over the following years, Laserlab-Europe expanded steadily in both size and scope. It strengthened access opportunities, integrated new user communities and broadened its scientific reach. In 2018, this evolution resulted in the formal establishment of Laserlab-Europe AISBL, providing a durable organisational framework to support the consortium's long-term mission.

Today, Laserlab-Europe acts as a coordinated European network that aligns the scientific, operational and technological development efforts of its member infrastructures through diverse joint projects. By enabling joint access schemes, most members open their laboratories to external users, allowing researchers from around the world to conduct experiments across a broad range of interdisciplinary fields, from fundamental laser science to applications spanning many areas of research and technology. Together with joint research projects, this strengthens the efficient use of cutting-edge facilities by both academic and industrial users and contributes to dynamic scientific and technological progress.

<https://laserlab-europe.eu/>